

WATER DIPLOMACY OF THE REPUBLIC OF TAJIKISTAN STRATEGY FOR SOLVING MODERN WORLD PROBLEMS

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Abstract: *The role of water diplomacy of the Republic of Tajikistan as a strategy for solving common global issues of today is related to environmental protection, efficient use of water resources in Tajikistan and Central Asian region, international cooperation and the country's environmental diplomacy with the countries of the world. Tajikistan, which is located in the Central Asian region is a country with abundant water resources and water and climate issues are of particular importance for it. The Republic of Tajikistan is an initiator of solving global problems in today's global issues. By using water resources, regional and international cooperation, Tajikistan can make a unique contribution as a strategic state to solving global water and environmental issues in the global and regional arena.*

Keywords: *global issues, sustainable development, water diplomacy, Republic of Tajikistan, Central Asia, foreign policy, initiatives of Tajikistan, transboundary cooperation, water issues, water resources, global initiatives, global problems, environmental issues, strategy, multilateral cooperation, strategic partnership.*

ВОДНАЯ ДИПЛОМАТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ ТАДЖИКИСТАН: СТРАТЕГИЯ РЕШЕНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ГЛОБАЛЬНЫХ ПРОБЛЕМ.

Аннотация: *Роль водной дипломатии Республики Таджикистан как стратегии решения современных глобальных проблем связана с охраной окружающей среды, эффективным использованием водных ресурсов в Таджикистане и Центральноазиатском регионе, международным сотрудничеством и экологической дипломатией страны со странами мира. Таджикистан, расположенный в Центральноазиатском регионе и обладающий богатыми водными ресурсами, имеет особое значение для себя в вопросах водоснабжения и климата. Республика Таджикистан выступает инициатором решения глобальных проблем современности. Используя водные ресурсы, региональное и международное сотрудничество, Таджикистан как стратегическое государство может внести уникальный вклад в решение глобальных проблем водоснабжения и охраны окружающей среды на глобальном и региональном уровнях.*

Ключевые слова: *глобальные проблемы, устойчивое развитие, водная дипломатия, Республика Таджикистан, Центральная Азия, внешняя политика, инициативы Таджикистана, трансграничное сотрудничество, водные проблемы, водные ресурсы, глобальные инициативы, глобальные проблемы, экологические проблемы, стратегия, многостороннее сотрудничество, стратегическое партнерство.*

The world today faces global issues that include a set of political, economic, environmental and social risks and problems, concern the interests of the entire population of the planet, and their solution is important for ensuring the economic and social progress of states and preserving human civilization.

Each country must contribute to solving modern global problems. In addition, environmental culture in countries should serve as a driving force.

In this regard, the Republic of Tajikistan has adopted a number of legal and regulatory documents aimed at regulating modern environmental issues within the framework of legislative and regulatory acts. Since independence, the Republic of Tajikistan has adopted 16 laws, one Strategy and two state programs [10-13]. The following programs are relevant to this area:

1. Comprehensive State Program for the Development of Environmental Education and Awareness among the Population of the Republic of Tajikistan for 2021-2026.
2. State Program for the Study and Protection of Glaciers in the Republic of Tajikistan for 2010-2030.

It should be noted that, given the importance of water and climate issues, the Republic of Tajikistan has been recognized as an initiator in this area within the UN. To five proposals from the Republic of Tajikistan have been voiced at a high level in prestigious international forums, and a resolution has been adopted with the support of the majority of UN member states, which we have summarized here:

1. First. 20 December 2000. Resolution No. 55/196 of the UN General Assembly, declaring the year 2003 the "International Year of Freshwater".
2. Second. Resolution No. 58/217 of the UN General Assembly of 23 December 2003, declaring the years 2005-2015 the "International Year of Freshwater". "International Decade for Action, "Water for Life"
3. Third. December 20, 2010. UN General Assembly Resolution No. 65/154, declaring 2013 the "International Year of Water Cooperation".
4. Fourth. December 21, 2016. UN General Assembly Resolution No. 71/222, declaring 2018-2028 the "International Decade for Action, "Water for Sustainable Development".
5. Fifth. December 14, 2022, the UN General Assembly, at its 77th session, at the proposal of Tajikistan and with the support of 153 Member States, declared 2025 the "International Year of Glaciers".

On March 23, 2023 at the proposal of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan, 2025 was declared the "International Year of Glaciers", which is timely for addressing environmental issues related to water resources and nature conservation.

In this regard, water diplomacy occupies a stable position in Tajikistan's foreign policy and is a means of peacefully resolving issues related to the management and use of water resources in the region's transnational rivers, which include not only the post-Soviet countries, but also Afghanistan, whose waterways are a source of water and flow into the Aral Sea. According to Tajik experts, strengthening the role of water diplomacy will contribute to solving water and energy issues in Central Asia [1].

Many countries in the world suffer from the negative consequences of water scarcity. This may be accelerated by the negative effects of climate change and global warming, which increase the risk of wars and conflicts over transboundary resources. Emphasis on water diplomacy with neighboring countries over transboundary resources is important for establishing cooperation and preventing conflicts.

If we consider the role of water diplomacy in this regard, it encompasses several approaches to solving global problems:

1. Water diplomacy plays an important role in formalizing transboundary water cooperation.
2. Water diplomacy recognizes the existence of various partnerships that can create conditions for resolving water conflicts and opportunities for cooperation in the water sector. In addition to formal diplomatic efforts, water diplomacy plays an important role in building trust and resolving conflicts between parties.
3. By combining technical and diplomatic tools, water diplomacy allows stakeholders to address complex regional and global water issues and respond to broader political conflicts.
4. Water diplomacy encompasses all measures taken by state and non-state actors to prevent or peacefully resolve conflicts (that arise) and to promote cooperation related to access, distribution or use

of water between states and non-state and private stakeholders. Such measures may include regional and sub-regional dialogues, agreements and memoranda of understanding between state authorities, formal mediation, legal evidence gathering, training and capacity building, exchange of interests, and exchange of information and knowledge.

In the concept of the foreign policy of the Republic of Tajikistan, in the diplomatic section on water cooperation, it is noted that "due to the growth of the population, the expansion of the area of agricultural land, the irrational use of water resources, climate change and environmental problems, the issues of drinking water shortage, the use of large and small transboundary rivers and other problems related to water are becoming factors that have a significant impact on international relations". [4]

Tajikistan's water diplomacy since 1999 The UN Conference on the Comprehensive Review of the Mid-Term Goals of the International Decade for Action, "Water for Sustainable Development, 2018-2028", held over three days at the UN Headquarters in New York, gave humanity hope for overcoming the water crisis. Therefore, this event took place at a time when it was necessary to choose a new, joint path and take proactive actions by all countries to overcome this problem. Thus, almost half a century later, the Second UN Conference was held at the initiative of the Republic of Tajikistan and the Kingdom of the Netherlands. While the first conference (in 1977) was held at the dawn of climate change, the second conference was held in conditions and circumstances when water and climate issues were becoming one of the most serious threats to humanity and life and nature were at risk.

Over the past two decades, the international initiatives of the Republic of Tajikistan in the field of water and its management under the leadership of Emomali Rahmon have become a chain of interconnected and mutually reinforcing links. While 2003 was declared the Year of Clean Water, in 2018 water was recognized as a key element in sustainable development. This means that water is recognized not only as a source of life (water makes up three-quarters of the human body), but also as an important element in the development of industry, agriculture, the economy and other sectors, and this is indeed the case. [9]

In a special interview with UN Television on the sidelines of the UN Conference on the Mid-Term Review of the International Decade for Action on Water for Sustainable Development, 2018-2028, the President of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon discussed water-related issues, emphasizing, among other things, that "Analysis shows that the state of water resources on the planet, especially fresh water, is deeply affected by various threats, including climate change, population growth, urbanization and industrialization, and is intensifying every year." Today, more than 50% of the world's population lives in areas where water is scarce for at least one month a year. Thirty percent of the world's population, approximately 2.1 billion people, do not have access to clean drinking water, and 60 percent of the world's population, or 4.5 billion people, do not have access to running water or sanitation. If this trend continues, the demand for water will increase by 40% from the current level by 2030 [8]. According to the above statistics, 1/4 of the world's population does not have access to clean drinking water. Tajikistan's international initiatives are mainly aimed at solving these issues. This factor has led to the melting of glaciers and rapid climate change. Therefore, the issue of water resource management and interaction with nature has become key in Tajikistan's initiatives.

The Second UN Conference on the Mid-Term Review of the Goals of the International Decade for Action, "Water for Sustainable Development, 2018-2028," is considered one of the main achievements of the foreign policy of the Republic of Tajikistan, as humanitarian values occupied a special place in its focus. The goal of Tajikistan's initiatives and actions is to save humanity and the planet Earth from the tragedy of extinction. In addition, resolving water issues plays an important role in maintaining peace and stability, global security, and preventing conflicts and armed conflicts between states. Therefore, if Tajikistan's initiatives are implemented and properly understood by the international community, hundreds of potential conflicts can be prevented. [6, p. 145]

World-renowned politicians and diplomats often welcome and support the proposals and initiatives of the Head of State of Tajikistan. It is for this reason that the Honorable Emomali Rahmon is known throughout the world for his comprehensive initiatives and role in solving global issues. Perhaps, to confirm the above, it is enough to quote the words of the UN representative about the Leader of the Nation and his initiatives. On September 20, 2010 in New York, at the UN General Assembly dedicated to the Millennium Development Goals, UN Deputy Secretary-General Sha Zi Kang stated: "President of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon is a world champion in solving water issues at the global level" [3, p. 208].

In general, the Republic of Tajikistan is actively pursuing water diplomacy and has set itself the goal of playing an active role in solving water issues at the global level. As part of this diplomacy and taking into account the constructive initiatives in the field of water resources, which have been highly appreciated by the international community, it is envisaged to implement new initiatives within the framework of regional and international organizations, primarily the UN. The aim of these actions is to reflect the need for constructive cooperation in resolving water issues in the interests of preserving life and sustainable development of humanity. Therefore, one of the priority areas of the foreign policy of the Republic of Tajikistan is to ensure the country's constructive role in water issues in the region and the international arena, which meets both national interests and the aspirations of the international community.

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